

THEORETICAL BASICS OF GENDER CHARACTERISTICS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This thesis discusses the theoretical factors of teaching foreign languages, taking into account gender characteristics. In order to study the gender characteristics of the students, the article developed a real questionnaire, including the analysis of the reasons for the students' reluctance to speak English with the representatives of the opposite gender and the students' tendency to work in groups.

Key words: gender approach, monologue, strategy, educational system, methodology, foreign languages.

Taking into account the characteristics of today's youth, research has shown that there is currently a serious problem of taking into account the individual characteristics of students in education, because in the modern educational environment, without taking into account the individual characteristics of each one, by working for a wide range of students educational goals seem impossible to achieve. In addition, there is little mention of an individual approach among teachers, and little attention is paid to studying the gender characteristics of students. Gender differences and cultural characteristics due to social reasons are one of the interesting phenomena in modern society. Their influence is not only in political life, but here women fight for their political rights.

Indeed, the discourse of gender differences is also present in the use of language to communicate, arguing that boys and girls differ in the way they communicate and therefore should be treated differently. Foreign research on the relationship between language and gender in the selection of exercises in English classes also finds differences in the use of language for communication in identifying differences between boys and girls. One of them is that girls are more polite than boys. When talking to same-sex peers, girls use different, positive politeness strategies. On the other hand, boys do not show it in such conditions. Boys do not follow the rules of politeness, conversation and interpersonal search, they tend to speak directly in conversation, referring to the rules of factual communication. Another difference is that girls are more passive than boys. They show that they are not sure what they are saying.

In fact, these differences are not only taken into account in lesson planning, but also play an important role in evaluating the results and work of students. J.G. Duskazieva gives her opinion on the main characteristics of the educational material by girls and boys: "Girls are dominant in the quantitative approach to learning the educational material, they are dominant in clear thinking, they are inclined to algorithms, templates and hard work, they intuition and prediction, the ability to analyze on an emotional basis, they are characterized by low speed of concentration in critical situations, but at the same time high selectivity indicators and attention span, addiction to monologue and story, large short-term memory capacity . Data from the experimental research base are the following factors that should be taken into account during the study of gender characteristics, in the teaching of foreign languages.

We developed an original questionnaire that included studying the reasons why students do not want to speak English with members of the opposite sex. Tendency of students to work in groups. Girls and boys differ in choosing to be active or passive in English lessons, behavior. It turns out that girls like to keep quiet more. Most boys prefer to be active, the rest can choose any work order. These results require revision. In an average English class, students are given more oral activity and responsibility. Girls, for example, do not want to talk to boys because they think they are arrogant. On the contrary, boys do not want to speak English with girls because girls are easily offended. Other reasons, mainly for girls and boys, are related to their lack of confidence in their ability to speak English, and therefore they believe that making mistakes in front of the opposite sex is a shame. Such patterns lead to restrictions, suppression and reduction of freedom of expression.

According to scientists, women see conversation as a way to develop and maintain intimacy, while for men, conversation is the key to negotiating and maintaining power to achieve a goal. As a result, interactions take place in a non-hierarchical way, and men view the world in a hierarchical way, so that during any interaction, one person occupies a higher position, and the other is lower. In other words, women interact in ways that promote solidarity. We took gender differences into account when evaluating lessons and student work. The development and implementation of the gender approach should begin with a clear understanding of the goals and specifics of this approach by teachers, learning the basics of mental development.

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